

Hydrolysis of 2-Phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-dione

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PROTECTION of a carbonyl group as its hydrazone, oxime, semicarbazone and other derivatives and the regeneration of the parent ketone from the derivative is of much synthetic interest. Quite a number of methods have been developed for this purpose¹. In the present paper we have studied hydrolysis of a hydrazone prepared from an active methylene compound with an objective of introducing a keto functionality in place of methylene. We have tried $\text{CuCl}_2/\text{methanol}$, $\text{TiCl}_3/\text{ethylene glycol}$, $\text{NaOCl}/\text{chloroform}$, $\text{NBS}/\text{methanol}$ and copper acetate/ $\text{methanol}/\text{Br}_2$ systems for the synthesis of desired compound.

Experimental

Copper(II) chloride, *N*-bromosuccinamide (NBS), TiCl_3 , sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl), bromine, methanol, ethylene glycol, aniline, acetoacetanilide, sodium nitrite and carbon tetrachloride were of high purity. Elemental analysis (C, H, N) was done on a Carlo-Erba elemental analyser. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer 977 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Carl-Ziess speord spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a Jeol JMX-DX-300 spectrometer.

2-Phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-dione²: A mixture of aniline (0.01 mol) dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (3 ml) and water (4 ml) was cooled to 0°. To it precooled sodium nitrite (0.01 mol) was added slowly. The diazonium ion so obtained was filtered into already cooled solution mixture of sodium acetate (8 g) and acetoacetanilide (0.01 mol) in alcohol (100 ml). The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 110°; ν_{max} 1 680, 1 650 (C=O), 1 550 (NH-N=C) and 3 110 cm^{-1} (NH); λ_{max} 27 500 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.45s (COCH₃), 11.25 (CONH), 13.50 (NH), 7.15–7.20 and 7.35–7.68 (ArH).

Hydrolysis of the hydrazone :

Method I: 2-Phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-dione (0.002 mol) was dissolved in methanol (100 ml) and aqueous solution of copper chloride (0.001 mol) was added to it. The contents were heated at 70° for 1 h, then cooled and the volume reduced. The coffee-coloured solid so formed was washed with water and ether, dried over silica gel and crystallised from hot ethanol, m.p. 209° (Found : C, 61.12; H, 4.26; N, 13.02%); ν_{max} 1 680 (C=O), 1 625 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N) and 1 540 cm^{-1} (NH); λ_{max} 27 000 cm^{-1} . The compound was identified as a copper complex (1).

Method II: Bromine (0.004 mol) in dry CCl_4 (4 ml) was added to a stirred solution of the copper complex (1; 0.002 mol) in dry CCl_4 (25 ml). The resulting copper bromide was filtered off and the filtrate was evaporated and on standing it gave yellow crystals which were recrystallised from CH_2Cl_2 to yield 2. m.p. 151° (Found : C, 43.74; H, 2.96%); λ_{max} 27 500 cm^{-1} ; ν_{max} 1 675 (C=O), 1 600 (C=C) and 1 550 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 11.25 and 13.50 (NH) disappear; λ_{max} 28 000 cm^{-1} ; m/z 438. which showed the presence of a bromine atom to hydrazone nitrogen and one bromine atom to anilide nitrogen.

Method III: 2-Phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-dione (500 mg) dissolved in chloroform (50 ml) was shaken with 5% NaOCl (20 ml) for 10 min. The organic layer was then separated, washed with water and dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 . Concentration of the organic layer gave yellow crystals of 3. m.p. 112° (Found : C, 60.75; H, 4.45; N, 13.30%); λ_{max} 27 300 cm^{-1} ; ν_{max} 1 670 (C=O) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=N); m/z 315. The nmr spectra showed the disappearance of a peak at δ 13.50 while other peaks remained intact.

Method IV: A mixture of 2-phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-dione (500 mg) dissolved in dry ethylene glycol (30 ml) and 20% aqueous solution of TiCl_3 (1.6 M; 90 ml) was refluxed for 30 min. The contents were then cooled, diluted with water, extracted with ether, washed with brine and dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 , m.p. 108° (Found : C, 68.34; N, 14.95; H, 5.35%); ν_{max} 1 660 (C=O), 1 580 (C=N) and 1 550 cm^{-1} (NH); m/z 280; nmr data being the same as reported for the starting material.

Method V: Powdered *N*-bromosuccinamide (4×10^{-2} mol) was added at 0–5° to an efficiently stirred 50% acetone-methanol solution. To it was added a suspension of 2-phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-dione (1×10^{-3} mol). Nitrogen evolution ceased within 1–3 min and the solution changed to red. Saturated aqueous sodium hydrogen sulphite was added to suppress the bromine formed. The solution was then heated for 10 min while adding water, cooled and shaken with ether. Ether was reduced in volume and the solution on standing gave crystals of 5 which were filtered, washed with cold ether and dried under reduced pressure, m.p. 135° (Found : C, 34.38; N, 4.00; H, 2.00%); ν_{max} 1 775, 1 745 cm^{-1} (C=O of CO-NBr), 1 708 (C=O of COCOCH₃), 1 600 (C=C phenyl) and 753 cm^{-1} (phenyl ring); m/z 350, 306, 288, 91, 71, 56, 43 and 15.

Method VI: Bromine (2×10^{-2} mol) was added at 0–5° to a stirred solution of the copper complex (1×10^{-2} mol) in methanol (50 ml). The solution was heated for 10 min while adding water (10 ml), then cooled and extracted with ether. Ether was removed and the product 5 was recrystallised from dichloromethane, m.p. 136° (Found : C, 34.38; N, 4.0; H, 2.00%); ν_{max} 1 775, 1 745 and 1 708 (C=O),

1 600 cm^{-1} (C=C), 753 cm^{-1} (phenyl ring); m/z 350, 306, 288, 91, 71, 56, 43 and 15.

Results and Discussion

The results show that only through methods V and VI the triketone was formed. The method I, where copper chloride was added, gave the copper complex (1) as a result of coordination using hydrazono-nitrogen and carbonyl group. The reason for this is that lability of the N-Cu bond is less for the system

under investigation and presence of carbonyl group leads to the formation of stable complex. This stability discourages the next step, that is, solvolysis or the oxidative lability of the other activated intermediate bonds in the intermediate. Similar results were obtained when Hg^{II} was used but when Pb^{IV} was the metal an internal redox in the intermediate gives rise to cleavage of the CH and N-Pb bonds giving the product. When Br_2 in CCl_4 was added to the couple-product no change was observed but when it was added as in method II to copper complex obtained by method I, it resulted in the formation of stable bromo product (2).

This kind of product has been proposed as intermediate in the conversion of hydrazones to ketones using NBS but as this reaction took place in CCl_4 , lability of N-Br bond is less in this medium thereby stabilising this product. This bromo compound when dissolved in alcohol and KI added, it liberated iodine giving back 2-phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-dione; here bromine atom forms HOBr which liberates iodine. Method III also gave a stable halogen compound 3 similar to 2.

The compounds of the types 2 and 3 are being reported for the first time and this can be a new method for the regioselective bromination and chlorination of hydrazones. In this system also N-Cl bond is not labile and further attack of OH^-

needed for deprotonation and the nucleophilic attack does not take place.

The product analysis of method IV shows that hydrazono group is not cleaved to produce a carbonyl compound and the starting compound is recovered at the end of the reaction. When 2-(nitrophenyl)hydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-dione was subjected to this system, reduction of nitro group to amino group takes place, which was proved by the dye test but the hydrazono group remained intact. It suggests that this reagent ($\text{TiCl}_3/\text{methanol}$) is not useful for hydrazone under investigation.

The product 5 obtained through method V shows that the band at 27 500 cm^{-1} in uv-visible spectra disappeared suggesting that the cleavage of the hydrazono group has taken place and possibly the triketone has been generated. The elemental analysis, ir and mass spectral studies suggest that the product formed is a triketone having a bromine atom attached to the anilide nitrogen and another bromine atom attached to the benzene ring. The presence of the bromine has been estimated using literature procedure. A following possible mechanism is proposed (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

An intermediate like 4 has been isolated using method II. The formation of intermediate like 2 from the copper chelate prompted us to extend this work to a system where copper complex- Br_2 -methanol was used in place of CCl_4 as solvent, as alcohol helps in solvolysis of the intermediate. The formation of triketone by using method VI not only supports the mechanism proposed for NBS-methanol system but also gives us a new system for the cleavage of hydrazono compounds. A possible system is as follows (Scheme 2).

The study concludes that in hydrazones having a coordinative site hydrolysis using various metal salts can not be achieved due to the stabilisation of N-M bond. The isolation of bromo and chloro compounds 2 and 3 respectively, helps in understanding the mechanism of hydrolysis using *N*-bromosuccinamide.

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